

Role Of Transesophageal Echo In Evaluating Left Ventricular Remodeling In Different Grades Of Ischemic Mitral Regurgitation In Subjects Undergoing Myocardial Revascularization Surgery With Or Without Concomitant Mitral Valve Procedure

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Abstract

Background

Ischemic Mitral Regurgitation (iMR) is a result of functional imbalance between mitral valve leaflets tethering and closing forces caused by left ventricular remodeling following myocardial infarction. The extent of global and regional LV remodeling can determine ischemic MR severity. Present study was aimed at evaluating degree of global and regional LV remodeling in subjects undergoing elective myocardial revascularization surgery with or without mitral valve procedure with different grades of ischemic MR.

Material and methods

196 subjects undergoing myocardial revascularization surgery ± mitral valve procedure were evaluated for baseline demographic, clinical and biochemical characteristics. Transesophageal echocardiography (TEE) was performed to assess presence and grading of ischemic MR and left ventricular remodeling using respective echo indices. MR was quantified using 2D vena contracta width (VCW), effective regurgitant orifice area (EROA), regurgitant volume (RVol) and regurgitant fraction (RF) into either “No” or “Mild,” “Moderate” and “Severe” ischemic mitral regurgitation (iMR) groups. Global LV remodeling was assessed using End diastolic & end systolic LV internal diameters, areas, and volumes, LV fractional shortening (LV-FS), fractional area change (LV-FAC), ejection fraction (LV-EF), systolic and diastolic sphericity indices (Si). Regional LV remodeling was assessed using regional wall motion score (RWMS) and score index (RWMSi), interpapillary muscle distances in systole (IPMDs) and diastole (IPMDd) and papillary muscle regional wall motion score index (PMWMSi) in different iMR grades and compared for statistical significance. and meaningful conclusions.

Results

In 196 subjects undergoing surgical myocardial revascularization, “Mild”, “Moderate”, and “Severe” iMR was observed in 67, 73 and 17 subjects and “No” iMR was found in 39 subjects respectively. LV Fractional shortening [33.08 ± 6.84 , 33.20 ± 8.79 , 26.05 ± 5.64 vs. 38.21 ± 8.56 (%) ($p < 0.0001$)], LV Fractional area change [53.72 ± 9.07 , 53.47 ± 11.94 , 43.84 ± 8.40 vs. 60.03 ± 10.62 (%) ($p < 0.0001$)] and, LV Ejection Fraction [48.30 ± 3.93 , 47.47 ± 3.46 , 46.31 ± 5.00 vs. 55.53 ± 5.60 (%) ($p < 0.0001$)], were significantly lower in “Mild”, “Moderate” and “Severe” iMR groups vs. “No” iMR group respectively. LV-systolic and diastolic sphericity indices [0.54 ± 0.34 , 0.56 ± 0.56 , 0.24 ± 0.10 vs. 0.53 ± 0.27 ($p = 0.038$)] and [0.54 ± 0.22 , 0.51 ± 0.29 , 0.35 ± 0.12 vs. 0.48 ± 0.15 ($p = 0.021$)] were significantly lower in “Severe” iMR group vs. “No” iMR group respectively. LV-Regional wall motion score and score index [23.45 ± 3.56 , 26.38 ± 4.32 , 24.24 ± 4.44 vs. 17.85 ± 2.98 ($p < 0.0001$)] and [1.46 ± 0.22 , 1.65 ± 0.27 , 1.51 ± 0.28 vs. 1.11 ± 0.19 ($p < 0.0001$)] , Posterior and Anterior papillary muscle wall motion score indices [1.48 ± 0.69 , 2.00 ± 0.91 , 1.66 ± 0.91 vs. 1.11 ± 0.32 ($p < 0.0001$)] and [1.25 ± 0.52 , 1.64 ± 0.76 , 1.49 ± 0.73 vs. 1.08 ± 0.20 ($p < 0.0001$)], Diastolic and Systolic interpapillary muscle distances (cm) [2.05 ± 0.30 , 2.11 ± 0.35 , 2.38 ± 0.34 vs. 1.99 ± 0.25 ($p < 0.0001$)] and [1.35 ± 0.31 , 1.39 ± 0.33 , 1.74 ± 0.33 vs. 1.22 ± 0.29 ($p < 0.0001$)] were significantly higher in “Mild”, “Moderate” and “Severe” iMR groups vs. “No” iMR group respectively.

Conclusion

Absence of ischemic MR or presence of a milder iMR had a better-preserved profile of global and regional LV remodeling. Increasing grades of iMR (moderate and severe) had worsened global and regional LV remodeling. There was a linear decrease in global and regional LV function with increasing grades of

ischemic MR. Reduced global and regional LV function predicted ischemic MR severity in patients undergoing surgical myocardial revascularization \pm mitral valve procedure.

Key words

Myocardial revascularization surgery, Global and regional LV remodeling, Ischemic mitral regurgitation, Vena contracta width, Effective regurgitant orifice area.

Text

Introduction

The mitral valve is situated between the left atrium and left ventricle to allow a unidirectional oxygenated blood flow from left atrium to left ventricle in a normal human heart.^[1] The “mitral valve apparatus” is a three-dimensional functional unit comprises of anterior and posterior mitral valve leaflets enclosed by a fibro-collagenous ring called ‘an annulus’ which holds these leaflets at the atrioventricular junction, ‘chordae tendineae’, multiple ligamentous structures which provide attachments of the MV leaflets to two or three muscular structures arising from left ventricular wall called “the anterolateral and posteromedial papillary muscles” and most importantly the “supporting left ventricular myocardial wall” from where the papillary muscles arise. ^[2,3,4] **(figure-1)**

Figure 1: 2D & 3D Transesophageal echocardiography to demonstrate components of “Mitral valve apparatus”. Image A) Trans Gastric 2 Chamber View (TG-2CV) obtained at (80-90°) showing mitral valve leaflets, chordae tendineae, papillary muscles and supporting left ventricular walls. B) 3D full volume single beat acquisition of mitral valve from LA perspective at midesophageal probe position and multiplane angle at (20-30°). Showing saddle shaped non-planer mitral valve annulus, anterior and posterior mitral leaflets, and commissures.

In cases of functional MR, the mitral valve leaflets are anatomically normal, rather there is a physiological mitral valve dysfunction secondary to myocardial dysfunction. ^[5,6] In case of ischemic MR, which occurs in

subjects with significant coronary artery disease following myocardial infarction, results from leaflets malcoaptation due to reduced closing forces and increased tethering forces on mitral valve leaflets. [6,7,8] Thus, iMR is a type of functional MR, a complication of myocardial infarction (MI), and not the fortuitous association of coronary artery disease with intrinsic (rheumatic or degenerative) valvular heart disease. [9,10,11]

This mechanistic change in mitral valve is a result of either an isolated posterior leaflet (asymmetric) tethering (in case of a previous inferior myocardial infarction) or bi-leaflet (anterior and posterior) (symmetric) tethering (in case of previous anterior myocardial infarction). Symmetric tethering leads to a central iMR (Allen carpentier's type I jet) while asymmetric tethering leads to eccentric iMR (Allen carpentier's type IIIb jet). [9,12] Presence of iMR is a marker of poor outcome and has major prognostic and therapeutic implications. [13] Nearly 41% candidates undergoing myocardial revascularization surgery (CABG) (CABG) may have associated iMR. [13, 14] Importantly, an uncorrected iMR even a milder one poses an increased risk for death and heart-failure hospitalization; hence, consideration for surgical repair or more aggressive perioperative medical management is needed to improve surgical outcome. [8, 15] In-hospital mortality rates for isolated CABG is 3% and 7- 20% for concomitant mitral procedure along with CABG respectively. [14,16] This significant difference in clinical outcomes makes preoperative evaluation of ischemic MR and its determinants using 2D and 3D Echocardiography a necessity to plan surgery and perioperative medical management. [17] Transesophageal echocardiography provides an excellent opportunity to evaluate iMR in anaesthetized subjects undergoing coronary bypass grafting surgery. [18] So, the present study was aimed at transesophageal echocardiographic evaluation of ischemic MR and degree of global and regional LV remodeling in subjects undergoing elective myocardial revascularization surgery (CABG) with or without concomitant mitral valve repair/replacement procedure. Echocardiographic indices of global and regional LV remodeling LV internal diameter, area, and volume obtained in end diastole and end systole, LV fractional shortening (LV-FS), fractional area change (LV-FAC), ejection fraction (LV-EF), systolic and diastolic sphericity index (Si) and regional LV remodeling i.e. regional wall motion score and index (RWMSi), interpapillary muscle distances (IPMD) in systole and diastole and papillary muscle regional wall motion score index (PMWMSi) were studied. (figure 2,3)

Figure 2: Measurement of left ventricular global remodeling indices, LV end diastolic volume (EDV), end systolic volume (ESV), LV ejection fraction (EF) and LV end diastolic (EDA), end systolic area (ESA), LV fractional area change (FAC) in A) mid esophageal 4 chamber view obtained @0° and B) Trans gastric mid short axis view obtained @0° at end systole and end diastolic phases of cardiac cycle respectively.

Figure 3: Measurement of left ventricular global remodeling using LV diastolic and systolic sphericity indices [Sphr(d) and Sphr(s)] respectively in A) mid esophageal 4 Chamber view obtained @0° and interpapillary muscle distances (IPMDd & IPMDs) respectively in B) Trans gastric mid short axis view obtained @0° end systole and end diastolic phases of cardiac cycle respectively.

Materials and Methods

This prospective observational study involved 204 subjects undergoing elective myocardial revascularization surgery for an angiographically diagnosed significant coronary artery disease in cardiovascular thoracic surgical unit of a tertiary care hospital in northern Karnataka, India from September 2018 to October 2019 after obtaining institutional ethical clearance (IEC ref no.: - KAHER/Ethic/2018-19/D-119) and informed consent from the study subjects. 204 subjects undergoing elective surgical myocardial revascularization (CABG) ± mitral valve procedure were included prospectively. Subjects with absolute contraindications for TEE probe insertion (n=2), those on pre-operative pharmacological or mechanical cardiovascular support [inotropes or Intra-aortic balloon counter pulsation (IABP) dependent subjects] (n=3) and those suffered myocardial infarction within 16 days before surgery (n=3), were excluded from the study. 2D transesophageal echocardiography was performed in 196 subjects fulfilling inclusion criteria to note the presence of and quantify ischemic MR if present. Comprehensive TEE evaluation was undertaken to evaluate global LV systolic function and indices of mitral deformation using x-matrix phased array transducer probe (X7-2t) mounted on Philips healthcare® Epic7C ultrasound workstation. The handling of the TEE probe was gentle and principle of as low as reasonably achievable (ALARA) was followed to avoid excessive heating of the TEE probe.^[19]

Echocardiographic assessment of ischemic MR severity:

Guidelines of the American Society of echocardiography were used to grade iMR severity. Using AHA/ACC updated guidelines for valvular heart diseases, the degree of severity of ischemic MR was graded and grouped into a “No iMR”, “Mild iMR”, “Moderate iMR” & “Severe iMR” groups as follows:

“**No iMR**” was defined as absence of any mitral regurgitation. “**Mild iMR**” was defined as MR regurgitant volume (RVol) <30 (ml/beat), regurgitant fraction (RF) <30%, effective regurgitant orifice area (EROA) <0.2 cm² and a vena contracta width of < 0.3 cm. “**Moderate iMR**” was defined as MR regurgitant volume

(RVol) between 30 - 59 (ml/beat), regurgitant fraction (RF) between 30-49%, effective regurgitant orifice area (EROA) between 0.2-0.39 cm² and vena contracta width of 0.3 to 0.69cm. “**Severe iMR**” was defined as a regurgitant volume (RV) ≥60 (ml/beat), regurgitant fraction (RF) ≥50 %, effective regurgitant orifice area (EROA) ≥0.4 cm² and vena contracta width of ≥0.7 cm. [15,20,21,22]

Assessment of global LV remodeling was done by measuring left ventricular (LV) end systolic and end diastolic diameter, fractional shortening (LV-FS) obtained using M-mode, LV end systolic and end diastolic area and fractional area change (LV-FAC) in trans gastric mid short axis (TG-mid Sax) view at papillary muscle level. Left ventricular volumes in end systole and end diastole and left ventricular ejection fraction (LV-EF) obtained using Simpson’s biplane method in midesophageal 4 chamber (ME4 Ch) view. Systolic and diastolic sphericity index (Si) were measured in midesophageal 4 chamber (ME4 Ch) view. Regional LV remodeling i.e. regional wall motion score and wall motion score index (RWMSi), interpapillary muscle distances (IPMD) in systole and diastole and papillary muscle regional wall motion score index (PMWMSi) were assessed using trans gastric basal, mid, and apical short axis views. [15, 23,24,25]

Statistical analysis

Data obtained from 196 subjects was tabulated and analyzed using Microsoft office Excel version 2016, Microsoft Corporation® One Microsoft Way, Redmond, Washington 98052-6399 USA, and IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows®, Version 20.0. Armonk, NY, USA. The Inter group comparison of quantitative data was analyzed with Z- score test statistics. Pearson’s chi square test statistics was used for intergroup comparison of qualitative data. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze significance in different grades of iMR. The significance was mentioned in terms of p-values. P-value more than 0.05 was considered non-significant (NS) while p-value of 0.05 and less was considered significant (S). P-value of less than 0.001 was considered highly significant (HS).

Results

The comparison of demographic, clinical and laboratory characteristics of the subjects in different groups of ischemic MR severity are shown in table. No. 1. The demographic study variables viz. age (p=0.29), sex (p=0.9), body surface area (BSA) (p=1.94), associated comorbidities viz. hypertension (p=0.1), diabetes mellites (DM) (p=0.47), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) (p=0.28), smoking (p=0.5), medication viz. β-blockers (p=0.86), prior percutaneous coronary intervention (p=0.122), and biochemistry viz. HbA_{1c} (p=0.061) and CK-MB levels (p=0.277) did not show any statistically significant difference in different groups of iMR grades. There was a statistically significant difference observed in variables like angiographic grade of coronary artery disease (p=0.043), type of myocardial infarction(p=0.0001), history of post MI thrombolytic therapy (p=0.0001), pharmacotherapy with

angiotensin II receptor blocker (p=0.0001), diuretics therapy (p=0.012) and nitrates (p=0.025) and preoperative serum creatinine levels (p=0.001) in different iMR groups.

There was a highly significant difference noted in transesophageal Echocardiographic indices of systolic global and regional LV remodeling. Left ventricular end diastolic and systolic diameters, areas and volumes were significantly higher in moderate and severe iMR category as compared to no or milder iMR categories (p<0.0001). Left ventricular (LV) fractional shortening (LV-FS), fractional area change (LV-FAC), ejection fraction (LV-EF) was significantly lower in severe iMR category compared to no or milder groups. (p<0.0001). Systolic and diastolic LV posterior wall thickness, percent change in LV posterior wall thickness, lateral and septal annular systolic (s') velocities (for all p<0.0001). LV systolic and diastolic sphericity indices were significantly low in severe iMR category (p<0.05). LV regional wall motion score & score index, papillary muscle wall motion score indices, systolic & diastolic interpapillary muscle distances were significantly higher (p<0.0001) in higher grades of iMR. Percent change in interpapillary distance were significantly lower in moderate and severe iMR category. (Table No.2).

Table No.1: - Comparison of demographic, clinical and biochemical characteristics of the subjects in different groups of ischemic MR severity

Demographic, Clinical and Biochemical Study Variable		Grade of Ischemic MR (n=196)				P-Value (Significance)
		No iMR (n=39) (Mean ±SD or (%))	Mild iMR (n=67) (Mean ±SD) or (%)	Moderate iMR (n=73) (Mean ±SD) or (%)	Severe iMR (n=17) (Mean ±SD) or (%)	
Age (Years)		60.18±9.92	59.93±8.99	59.96±8.7	54.24±12.63	0.29(NS)
Sex	Male	27(19%)	50(34%)	55(38%)	13(9%)	0.9 (NS)
	Female	12 (24%)	17(33%)	18(35%)	4(8%)	
BSA (kg/m ²)		1.69±0.14	1.68±0.16	1.71±0.15	1.72±0.15	1.94 (NS)
NYHA Class		1.97±0.67	2.03±0.7	2.07±0.77	2.00±0.79	0.927 (NS)
Hypertension	Yes	30 (20%)	51(34%)	56(37%)	13(9%)	0.1 (NS)
	No	9 (20%)	16 (35%)	17 (37%)	4 (8%)	
Diabetes Mellites	Yes	26(22%)	42(36%)	41(35%)	8(7%)	0.47 (NS)
	No	13(16%)	25(32%)	32(41%)	9(11%)	
COPD	Yes	10(24%)	12(29%)	18(45%)	1(2%)	0.28 (NS)
	No	29 (19%)	55(35%)	55(35%)	16(11%)	
Smoking	Yes	14(25%)	17(31%)	21(38%)	3(5%)	0.50 (NS)
	No	25(18%)	50(35%)	52(37%)	14(10%)	
Angiographic Grade of CAD	CAD-RAD4A	14(19.1%)	24(32.9%)	20(27.4%)	15(20.6%)	0.043 (S)
	CAD-RAD4B	14(25.5%)	20(36.4%)	19(34.5%)	2(3.6%)	
	CAD-RAD5	21(18.3%)	40(34.8%)	45(39.1%)	9(7.8%)	
Preop β-Blockers	Yes	33(20%)	57(34%)	65(38%)	14(8%)	0.86 (NS)
	No	6(22%)	10(37%)	8(30%)	3(11%)	
Preop AT II RB	Yes	18(17%)	28(26%)	49(45%)	13(12%)	<0.001(HS)
	No	21(24%)	39(44%)	24(27%)	4(5%)	
Preop Nitrates	Yes	29(19%)	52(34%)	60(39%)	13(8%)	0.025 (S)
	No	10(24%)	15(36%)	13(30%)	4(10%)	
Preop Diuretics	Yes	12(12%)	30(32%)	44(45%)	11(11%)	0.012(S)
	No	27(26.5%)	37(37%)	29(29.5%)	6(7%)	
Type of MI	NSTEMI	17(63%)	5(19%)	2(7%)	3(11%)	<0.0001(HS)
	AWMI	14(20%)	27(38%)	23(32%)	7(10%)	
	AWMI+LE	3(15%)	8(40%)	8(40%)	1(5%)	
	AW+IWMI	1(13%)	2(25%)	4(50%)	1(13%)	
	IWMI	4(6%)	25(36%)	36(51%)	5(7%)	

Prior PCI	Yes	10(37%)	7(26%)	8(30%)	2(7%)	0.122(NS)
	No	29(17%)	60(36%)	65(38%)	15(9%)	
Thrombolysis	Yes	10(37%)	7(26%)	8(30%)	2(7%)	<0.0001(HS)
	No	29(17%)	60(36%)	65(38%)	15(9%)	
HbA1C (gm/dl)		8.46±2.54	7.62±2.00	7.48±2.19	6.97±1.86	0.061 (NS)
Sr. Creat (mg/dl)		1.08±0.25	1.04±0.22	1.14±0.30	1.37±0.55	<0.0001 (HS)
CK-MB (IU/Lit)		29.33±10.71	30.21±13.96	26.51±9.71	29.24±10.24	0.277(NS)

(BSA: - Body Surface Area, COPD: - Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease, CAD: - Coronary Artery Disease, AT II RB: - Angiotensin II Receptor Blocker, MI: - Myocardial Infarction, PCI: - Percutaneous Coronary Intervention. Sr. Creat. :- Serum Creatinine, CK-MB: - Creatine Kinase – Muscle & Brain.)

Table 2: - Comparison of Transesophageal Echocardiographic Global and regional LV remodeling indices in different grades of Ischemic mitral regurgitation

Echocardiographic Indices of Global and Regional LV Remodeling	Grade Of Ischemic Mitral Regurgitation				P- Value & Significance
	No (n=39) Mean±SD	Mild (n=67) Mean±SD	Moderate (N=73) Mean±SD	Severe (n=17) Mean±SD	
LVID (d) (cm)	4.19±0.48	4.22±0.49	4.40±0.60	4.98±0.73	<0.0001(HS)
LVID (s) (cm)	2.59±0.49	2.83±0.50	2.96±0.66	3.68±0.65	<0.0001(HS)
LV Fractional Shortening (%)	38.21±8.56	33.08±6.84	33.20±8.79	26.05±5.64	<0.0001(HS)
LV Area (d) (cm ²)	13.79±3.21	14.01±3.20	15.33±4.31	19.64±6.05	<0.0001(HS)
LV Area (s) (cm ²)	5.51±2.18	6.58±2.32	7.27±3.62	11.05±4.07	<0.0001(HS)
LV-FAC (%)	60.03±10.62	53.72±9.07	53.47±11.94	43.84±8.40	<0.0001(HS)
LV Volume (d) (ml)	77.27±12.99	86.8±10.88	88.99±10.33	92.59±10.17	<0.0001(HS)
LV Volume (s) (ml)	34.61±8.09	44.98±7.20	46.76±6.36	49.88±8.26	<0.0001(HS)
LV-EF (%)	55.53±5.60	48.30±3.93	47.47±3.46	46.31±5.00	<0.0001(HS)
LV PWT (d) (cm)	0.94±0.12	0.91±0.11	0.86±0.11	0.91±0.13	<0.0001(HS)
LV PWT (s) (cm)	1.35±0.21	1.17±0.18	1.02±0.21	1.13±0.20	<0.0001(HS)
Change in LV PWT (%)	29.63±8.09	21.08±10.06	13.47±14.05	17.65±14.45	<0.0001(HS)
LV Systolic SI	0.53±0.27	0.54±0.34	0.56±0.56	0.24±0.10	0.038(S)
LV Diastolic SI	0.48±0.15	0.54±0.22	0.51±0.29	0.35±0.12	0.021(S)
LV Regional WMS	17.85±2.98	23.45±3.56	26.38±4.32	24.24±4.44	<0.0001(HS)
LV Regional WMSi	1.11±0.19	1.46±0.22	1.65±0.27	1.51±0.28	<0.0001(HS)
Lateral TDI- Ann S vel (cm/s)	6.81±1.22	6.88±1.42	6.06±1.37	5.38±1.10	<0.0001(HS)
Tei Index	0.59±0.09	0.58±0.08	0.60±0.10	0.59±0.10	0.518(NS)
Septal TDI- Ann S vel (cm/s)	5.67±1.02	5.73±1.18	5.05±1.14	4.48±0.92	<0.0001(HS)
Posterior PM WMSi	1.11±0.32	1.48±0.69	2.00±0.91	1.66±0.91	<0.0001(HS)
Anterior PM WMSi	1.08±0.20	1.25±0.52	1.64±0.76	1.49±0.73	<0.0001(HS)
IPMD in Diastole (cm)	1.99±0.25	2.05±0.30	2.11±0.35	2.38±0.34	<0.0001(HS)
IPMD in Systole (cm)	1.22±0.29	1.35±0.31	1.39±0.33	1.74±0.33	<0.0001(HS)
Change in IPMD (%)	38.29±10.63	34.38±7.81	34.22±9.72	26.88±6.60	<0.0001(HS)

(LV :- Left Ventricle, LVID: - Left Ventricular Internal Diameter, FS :- Fractional Shortening, FAC: - Fractional Area Change, EF :- Ejection Fraction, PWT :- Posterior Wall Thickness, Si :- Sphericity Index, WMS :- Wall Motion Score, WMSi :- Wall Motion Score index, MV: - Mitral Valve, PML: - Posterior Mitral Leaflet, Ann: - Annulus, Cumm: - Commissure, IPMD :- Interpapillary Muscle Distance, TDI :- Tissue Doppler Imaging, d :- Diastolic, s :- Systolic)

Discussion

In present study, transesophageal echocardiographic evaluation of 196 subjects undergoing elective myocardial revascularization surgery (CABG) were evaluated for presence of ischemic mitral regurgitation (iMR) and were grouped according to their grades of severity into “No”, “Mild”, “Moderate” and “Severe” iMR categories. Baseline demographic, clinical, biochemical were noted. Echocardiographic indices of global and regional left ventricular (LV) remodeling were recorded in different grades of iMR and compared for statistical significance. The extent of global and regional LV remodeling was evaluated using LV internal diameter, area, and volume obtained in end diastole and end systole, LV fractional shortening (LV-FS), fractional area change (LV-FAC), ejection fraction (LV-EF), systolic and diastolic sphericity index (Si), s' velocities of lateral & septal annular tissue doppler imaging. Regional LV remodeling i.e. regional wall motion score and index (RWMSi), interpapillary muscle distances (IPMD) in systole and diastole and papillary muscle regional wall motion score index (PMWMSi) used to assess the regional LV remodeling in different iMR groups.

Graph 1: - Degree of Global and regional LV remodeling in different grades of ischemic MR

(Graph 1: -1- There was increase in LV diastolic volume, regional wall motion score, Posterior and Anterior papillary muscle wall motion score index and diastolic interpapillary muscle distance with increasing grade of ischemic mitral regurgitation

severity. Left ventricular fractional shortening, fractional area change, ejection fraction, posterior wall thickness, systolic and diastolic sphericity index were reduced with increasing grade of ischemic MR.

Graph 2: - Linearity in relationship between LV remodeling indices and grade of ischemic MR

(Graph 2: - Horizontal axis: - Grade of ischemic mitral regurgitation severity 1- "No iMR", 2. "Mild iMR", 3. "Moderate iMR", 4. "Severe iMR". There is a linear increase in LV diastolic volume ($R^2=0.9015$), Regional wall motion score ($R^2=0.6148$), Posterior ($R^2=0.5742$) and Anterior ($R^2=0.6997$) wall motion score index. There is a linear decrease in left ventricular fractional shortening ($R^2=0.8816$), fractional area change ($R^2=0.7798$), ejection fraction ($R^2=0.8903$), posterior wall

thickness ($R^2=0.6715$), systolic ($R^2=0.3973$) and diastolic ($R^2=0.8687$) sphericity index and percent change in interpapillary muscle distance ($R^2=0.5123$).

Demographic characteristics, age ($p=0.29$), sex ($p=0.9$), body surface area (BSA) ($p=1.94$), NYHA class ($p=0.927$), clinical comorbidities like hypertension ($p=0.1$), diabetes mellites (DM) ($p=0.47$), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) ($p=0.28$), smoking ($p=0.5$), pharmacotherapy with β -blockers ($p=0.86$), history of prior percutaneous coronary intervention ($p=0.122$), and biochemical indicator of diabetic control, HbA1c levels ($p=0.061$) and myocardial injury, CK-MB levels ($p=0.277$) were distributed evenly in all the grades of ischemic MR and did not determine its severity. Valuckiene Z et al found similar results except increasing age and female sex determined severity of iMR.^[24] In our study, higher angiographic grade of coronary artery disease (CAD-RAD Grade 4B and 5) determined higher grades of iMR ($p=0.043$). Non-ST segment elevation MI determined lower grades of iMR while anterior, inferior and combine anterior+inferior wall MI determined higher grades of iMR ($p<0.0001$). Subjects who received post MI thrombolytic therapy, had lower grades of iMR ($p<0.0001$). Valuckiene Z et al observed similar results in their study.^[24] Subjects with ischemic MR were more often on angiotensin II receptor blockers ($p<0.0001$) This pharmacotherapeutic strategy reduces the iMR severity as documented by Kang DH et al (PRIME study) and Lee S et al.^[25,26] pre operative use of diuretics ($p=0.012$) and nitrates (vasodilators) ($p=0.025$) also reduces the severity of iMR as evaluated by Stevenson LW et al.^[27] Sr. creatinine levels were significantly higher in higher grades of iMR ($p<0.0001$), a similar observation was made by Seghatol FF et al in subjects with ischemic MR following acute myocardial infarction.^[28] Present study shows LV fractional shortening (LV-FS) ($p<0.0001$), LV fractional area change (LV-FAC) ($P<0.001$) and LV ejection fraction ($p<0.0001$) exhibited more impaired trends with higher grades of iMR. End systolic and end diastolic LV dimensions, areas and volumes were significantly higher in severe and moderate grades of ischemic MR. Similar observation was made by Litwin SE et al in experimental study on rats where induced myocardial infarction showed higher LV end systolic and end diastolic dimensions and volumes.^[29] In ischemic MR with symmetric tethering, LV end-systolic and end-diastolic volumes and the sphericity index correlate with the severity of MR. [15] this can be attributed to degree of LV dilatation directly relates to apical displacement of papillary muscles, conversely this is not so in cases of asymmetric tethering phenotypes where the measures of global LV remodeling do not robustly correlate with severity of MR as posterior infarcts can disrupt papillary muscle geometry and generate severe MR.[15] In such cases the indices of mitral valve deformation are better predictors of iMR severity than the global and regional LV remodeling. In mixed (both type I and IIIb) iMR category, LV dilatation would therefore not be an independent predictor of iMR severity. [15] In present study this categorization was not done to independently study the types of iMR jets and association of iMR severity and LV global or regional function indices of such in a population with mixed CIMR phenotypes. [15] The papillary muscles are

oriented parallelly in their long axes to that of the LV and perpendicularly to the plane of the mitral annulus. Disruption caused by myocardial infarction radically changes the relationship of papillary muscles relative to each other and to the valve apparatus. This effect creates a substrate for iMR.^[15]

In present study evaluation of ischemic MR and global and regional LV remodeling was done using transesophageal Echocardiography (TEE). TEE provides an excellent opportunity to evaluate the ischemic MR and global and regional LV remodeling in operating room prior to myocardial revascularization surgery (CABG) under general anesthesia with endotracheal tube in situ.^[18,19] Performing transesophageal echocardiography and analyzing global and regional LV remodeling becomes more feasible however, because of vasodilating effects of anesthesia, iMR severity may be underestimated by intraoperative TEE.^[29,30] One proposed tactic to ensure appropriate severity grading is to administer vasopressor or assessing the MR just after the sternotomy when the effect of anaesthesia on afterload is balanced by surgical stimulus in relatively shallow plane of anaesthesia. ^[30,31] Both these methods to mitigate effect of anaesthesia on afterload were used in our study to minimize underestimation of iMR.

Study based on left ventricular (LV) strain done by Valuckiene Z et al has concluded that LV ejection fraction (LV-EF) and longitudinal myocardial deformation (sphericity) parameters were significantly better in healthy subjects, but were comparable in milder and higher grades of iMR but when circumferential myocardial deformation parameters were significantly worse in iMR group compared to healthy subjects and milder MR group. Global, basal, and mid-ventricular radial strain was significantly lower in iMR group compared to both—healthy subjects and milder MR group. In our study the sphericity indices of LV, a comparable match with the longitudinal deformation was marginally significant in higher iMR group compared to milder or no iMR group. ^[24] Nouri M et al concluded that tenting area (TA) was significantly correlated with annulus diameter and, along with sphericity index and C-septal, were the independent echocardiographic determinants of MR severity. In present study higher systolic and diastolic sphericity determined the severity of iMR.^[32] Cavalcante JL et al concluded in their study that a global LV remodeling, regional inferior myocardial scarring and mitral valve geometry were important predictors of worsening MR than total infarct size in subjects with advanced ischemic cardiomyopathy. We had a similar observation in our study where global LV remodeling and higher grades of regional wall motion were associated with iMR.^[33] Qiao L et al found higher wall motion score index as a predictor of persistent moderate or severe secondary (ischemic) MR and had independent negative prognostic value. We had a similar finding as the higher wall motion score was associated with increased ischemic MR. ^[34] Bouma et al concluded that the prevalence of iMR is almost doubled in the presence of papillary muscle infarction and higher regional wall motion score index. iMR severity was predicted by tenting height and interpapillary muscle distance independent predictors of iMR.^[35] In present study, both diastolic and systolic interpapillary muscle distances predicted severity of ischemic MR. Our finding of higher values of

posterior mitral leaflet systolic tenting angle associating with higher grades of ischemic MR reinvokes the findings by Leśniak-Sobelga A et al their study, the anterior as well as posterior mitral leaflet angles correlated well with the severity of iMR along with other determinants like extent of mitral apparatus deformation and LV remodeling.^[36] In our study we could correlate the severity of iMR with LV remodeling indices and thus they can also be determinants of iMR severity along with mitral valve deformation.

Limitations

1. In present study transesophageal Echocardiography was performed after induction of general anaesthesia with endotracheal tube (GA+ETT). The effect of anaesthesia on loading conditions can alter grading of iMR.
2. Subgrouping of Ischemic MR into symmetric and asymmetric (Allen carpentier's type I and IIIb respectively) was not considered in present study. It could have given a better insight into the pathophysiology of iMR resulting from left ventricular remodeling. This can form a basis for future research on this topic.
3. Though care was taken to avoid foreshortening of midesophageal 4 chamber view, there can be a variation in 2D plane obtained for measurements of left ventricular volumes, ejection fraction (LV-EF) and LV sphericity indices.
4. Evaluation of LV function with tissue doppler imaging (medial and lateral S' velocity) is validated for transthoracic echo (TTE). The validity for transesophageal echo is still to be established. The discussion on this is out of the scope of present article.

Conclusion

Worse global and regional LV remodeling was seen with moderate and severe forms of ischemic MR. The echo indices of global and regional LV remodeling were better maintained in subjects with mild or absent ischemic MR. Transesophageal Echocardiographic indices of global and regional LV remodeling significantly predicted severity of ischemic MR in subjects undergoing myocardial revascularization surgery.

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Conflicts of interest

Nil.

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